

Measurement of Exchangable Ions of Clays in Different Suites

A. K. NAG and A. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta 700012

Manuscript received 14 May 1974; revised 24 February 1975; accepted 29 April 1975

The ease of exchange of a particular cation at different degrees of saturation was studied by equilibrating each of the hetero-ionic system $\text{NH}_4\text{-Ca-clay}$, $\text{Ca-NH}_4\text{-clay}$, Zn-Cr-clay , Cr-Zn-clay and Ni-Cu-clay , Cu-Ni-clay with H-resin taken in cellophane bags. In each binary clay, the ion (in the form of a salt) that is added last, is exchanged to a greater extent. This shows that binding energy of all the ions to the clay surface is not the same. The cation that is added first, is "firmly" bound to the clay surface and thus is more difficult to exchange, where as the cation that is added last is rather "loosely" bound to the clay surface and hence can be exchanged more easily.

THE clay surface behaves as a heterogeneous system so far as the bonding of ions to it is concerned. For, a given ion can not only be adsorbed to different clay minerals with different bonding energies, because the lattice forces are different. but with regard to the same clay mineral also, a particular cation may be adsorbed with different bonding energies. This was envisaged by

different workers¹⁻¹³.

In the present investigation, the technique of Brown and Albrecht¹⁴ has been used to observe the difference in exchangeability of some binary clays, which have been saturated with different proportions of a pair of cations, Ca^{+2} and NH_4^{+1} , Zn^{+2} and Cr^{+3} and Ni^{+2} and Cu^{+2} but having somewhat known exchange characteristics.

TABLE 1. REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND CLAY CONTAINING Ca^{+2} AND NH_4^{+1} IONS

Type of clay	Ratio		% of NH_3 exchanged		% of a Ca exchanged	
	Ca	NH_4	Of the total exchange-able ions	Of the total exchange-able NH_3	Of the total exchange-able ions	Of the total exchange-able Ca
$\text{Ca-NH}_4\text{-clay}$	70	30	10.07	33.56	53.23	76.04
$\text{NH}_4\text{-Ca-clay}$	70	30	14.61	48.70	16.60	23.70
$\text{Ca-NH}_4\text{-clay}$	50	50	14.70	28.14	42.29	84.58
$\text{NH}_4\text{-Ca-clay}$	50	50	15.70	30.14	14.15	28.30
$\text{Ca-NH}_4\text{-clay}$	30	70	10.40	14.85	14.05	46.83
$\text{NH}_4\text{-Ca-clay}$	30	70	15.50	22.14	1.86	6.20

TABLE 2—REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND CLAY CONTAINING Ni^{2+} AND Cu^{2+} IONS

Type of clay	Ratio		% of Ni exchanged		% of Cu exchanged	
	Ni	Cu	Of the total exchange-able ions	Of the total exchange-able Ni	Of the total exchange-able ions	Of the total exchange-able Cu
Ni-Cu-clay	3	1	24.6	32.9	6.9	27.4
Cu-Ni-clay	5	2	3.3	4.7	15.4	51.7

TABLE 3—REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND CLAY CONTAINING Zn^{2+} AND Cr^{3+} IONS

Type of clay	Ratio		% of Cr exchanged		% of Zn exchanged	
	Zn	Cr	Of the total exchange-able ions	Of the total exchange-able Cr	Of the total exchange-able ions	Of the total exchange-able Zn
Cr-Zn-clay	9	11	37.8	68.9	9.2	20.3
Zn-Cr-clay	4	1	4.3	23.5	32.9	40.2

Experimental

NH₄-Ca-clay was prepared by first treating the H-clay with pure CaCO₃ required to attain a definite degree of saturation, boiling off CO₂ after equilibration, then adding NH₄OH to complete the saturation. Ca-NH₄-clay was similarly prepared by adding to H-clay first NH₄OH and then CaCO₃.

Cr-Zn- and Zn-Cr-clays, and Ni-Cu- and Cu-Ni-clays were also prepared in a similar manner by leaching the H-clay with the salt solutions of the respective ions.

The mixed clays were then allowed to exchange for the H⁺-ions of H-resin taken in cellophane bags in the manner described in earlier paper^{16,17}.

Results and Discussion

On comparing the NH₄-Ca-clay and Ca-NH₄-clay having the same proportion of NH₄⁺ and Ca²⁺ it is found that NH₄⁺ in the former is exchanged in a larger amount than in the latter. On the other hand, Ca²⁺ in the latter is more readily replaced by H⁺-ions of H-resin than in the former. This shows that the same cation is not exchangeable to the same extent although present in the same proportion showing that it is not adsorbed by the clay in the same manner.

In the case of Cr-Zn-clay and Zn-Cr-clay the differentiation between the exchangeability of either Cr³⁺ or Zn²⁺ is similarly evident, although both ions are not present in the same proportion. Similar observations are also found regarding the exchangeability of Cu²⁺ or Ni²⁺ ions in Ni-Cu-clay systems.

It becomes evident that all the ions are not bound with the same bonding energy to the clay surface i.e., variable sites are likely to be present on the clay surface.

References

1. G. WIEGNER and MITCHELL, *J. Land.*, 1912, **60**, 111, 197.
2. G. WIEGNER, *Trans. Intern. Cong. Soil Sci.* 3rd Congr. Oxford, 1935, **5**, 111.
3. A. GANGULY and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1952, **56**.
4. C. E. MARSHALL, *Soil Sci.*, 1948, **65**, 57.
5. O. BOTTINI, *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, **78**, 68.
6. A. P. VANSELOW, *Soil Sci.*, 1932, **33**, 95.
7. J. N. MUKHERJEE, Special Publication, I.A.C.S., Calcutta, No. XIII, 1947.
8. R. P. MITRA and B. S. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 216.
9. A. H. TRUESDELL and C. L. CHRIST, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1968, **266**, 402.
10. A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**,
11. C. E. MARSHALL, "The Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals", Academic Press Inc., N.Y.
12. R. P. MITRA, *Indian Soc. Soil Sci. Bull.*, 1941, **4**, 21.
13. R. E. GRIM, "Clay Mineralogy", McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1953.
14. D. A. BROWN and WM A. ALBRECHT, *Res. Bull. No. 477, College of Agric. Univ. of Mo.*, 1950.
15. A. RENOLD, *Kolloid Buch*, 1936, **43**, 1.
16. A. K. NAG and A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 101.
17. A. K. NAG and A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 393.
18. A. K. GANGULY, *J. Phys. & Coll. Chem.*, 1951, **55**, 1417.